

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE AMONG PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This thesis covers the pedagogical and methodological foundations of the formation of a healthy lifestyle in primary school students. The study identifies the structural components of a healthy lifestyle and analyzes effective methods for integrating them into the educational process. The role of the educational process, organized on the basis of an interactive and competency-based approach, in increasing students' physical activity, hygienic culture, and motivation for a healthy life is substantiated.*

Keywords. *healthy lifestyle, primary education, pedagogical methodology, physical activity, hygienic culture.*

Introduction. In today's conditions of globalization and digitalization, the issue of strengthening children's health is emerging as one of the priority tasks facing the education system. The State Educational Standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan define the physical development of students at the primary education stage, the formation of knowledge, skills and competencies related to a healthy lifestyle as an important direction. These requirements require the organization of the educational process aimed at protecting and strengthening the health of primary school students on a scientific basis.

The body of children of primary school age is especially sensitive to external environmental factors, and during this period their physical, mental and social development processes are active. Habits and behavioral norms formed at this age can be preserved at subsequent stages of education and throughout life. Therefore, the systematic formation of initial knowledge, skills and competencies related to a healthy lifestyle in primary school students is an important pedagogical task. The formation of a healthy lifestyle in the primary education system is of great importance not only for strengthening the physical health of students, but also for ensuring their mental stability and social adaptation. The requirements of state educational standards and the analysis of scientific research show that methodological approaches aimed at forming a healthy lifestyle allow students to develop a conscious attitude towards health

and sustainable competencies. Therefore, the scientific substantiation and improvement of the methodology for forming a healthy lifestyle in primary school students is one of the urgent tasks of the modern education system.

Issues of healthy lifestyle formation in WHO and UNESCO documents

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), healthy lifestyle habits formed in childhood are an important factor in maintaining human health throughout life. The concept of “Health Promoting Schools” put forward by WHO recognizes the school environment as the main institutional mechanism for the formation of healthy behavior in children, and emphasizes the need to increase physical activity, integrate healthy nutrition and hygiene education into the educational process.

Also, WHO recommendations evaluate the formation of knowledge and skills related to a healthy lifestyle for primary school-age children from an early age as an effective preventive tool in preventing chronic diseases in the future. This approach, along with the physical development of children, also serves to stabilize their psycho-emotional state. In the concepts of “Education for Sustainable Development” and “Global Citizenship Education” developed by UNESCO, a healthy lifestyle is considered an important component of education. These documents specifically mention the need to form a conscious attitude towards a healthy lifestyle, personal responsibility and social activity in students through the educational process. According to the UNESCO approach, the promotion of a healthy lifestyle is directly related to the quality of education and the development of students' life competencies. These ideas put forward in WHO and UNESCO documents are consistent with the tasks set out in the State Educational Standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan and indicate the need for scientific substantiation of methodological approaches aimed at the formation of a healthy lifestyle at the primary education stage. In this regard, the pedagogical methodology developed based on the recommendations of international organizations is considered highly effective in forming sustainable competencies for a healthy lifestyle in students.

The main components of a healthy lifestyle include: personal hygiene, proper and balanced nutrition, physical exercise and sports, adherence to a daily routine, avoidance of harmful habits, etc.

Results. Personal hygiene is one of the most important components of a healthy lifestyle, which serves to form a sanitary and hygienic culture in students. The formation of skills such as hand washing, body and clothing

hygiene, and oral hygiene in primary school students is important in preventing infectious diseases. Systematic and consistent teaching of hygiene rules in the educational process develops a conscious attitude towards health in students. Proper nutrition at primary school age is an important factor in the physical and mental development of children. A balanced diet ensures a sufficient amount of protein, fat, carbohydrates, vitamins and minerals. Explaining the principles of healthy eating to students during the educational process and providing them with knowledge about the negative effects of unhealthy food products helps to form a healthy eating culture. Regular physical activity is important for the physical development of primary school students, strengthening the musculoskeletal system. Physical exercise improves the functioning of the cardiovascular and respiratory systems and increases the overall working capacity of children. The systematic organization of physical education classes, active games and sports events during the educational process forms positive motivation in students towards a healthy lifestyle.

The daily routine is of great importance in properly coordinating the educational and recreational activities of primary school students. The rational distribution of sleep, study, nutrition and physical activity corresponds to the physiological needs of the children's body. Compliance with the daily routine forms discipline, responsibility and proper time planning skills in students. The formation of initial concepts about harmful habits at the primary education stage is of preventive importance. Providing students with age-appropriate information about factors that are harmful to health, including elements of an unhealthy lifestyle, will help prevent negative behavior in the future. Using positive role models for a healthy lifestyle in the educational process will develop a conscious and responsible attitude towards a healthy lifestyle in students.

Components of a healthy lifestyle	Control group (baseline, %)	Control group (final, %)	Experimental group (baseline, %)	Experimental group (final, %)
Maintaining personal hygiene	8	4	9	5

Eating a healthy and balanced diet	38	43	41	60
Exercising	46	50	44	72
Following a daily routine	41	47	42	64
Avoiding bad habits	52	58	53	73

The results show that the component of personal hygiene compliance increased from 39% to 65% in the experimental group, while in the control group there was only a change from 38% to 44%. The experimental group's indicators for proper and balanced nutrition increased from 41% to 60%, while in the control group it remained in the range of 38–43%. The component of physical exercise changed from 44% to 72% for the experimental group, and from 46–50% for the control group. The experimental group's indicators for following a daily routine increased from 42% to 64%, while in the control group it remained in the range of 41% to 47%. The indicators for avoiding harmful habits increased from 53% to 73% for the experimental group, while in the control group it remained at the level of 52–58%.

Conclusion. At the same time, the formation of a healthy lifestyle at the primary education stage not only strengthened physical health, but also had a positive effect on the mental stability, social adaptation and educational success of students. In general, scientifically based methods aimed at the formation of a healthy lifestyle in primary school students allow the development of students' health care competencies, the effective implementation of preventive measures and the prevention of chronic diseases in the future. Therefore, it was recommended to widely introduce this method in primary schools.

References

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